

Analysis

Operator: Lindemann
Sample ID: Ceroxid, nano, 2000151
Sample Desc:
Sample Weight: 0.835 g

Date: 2022/01/11

Filename:

Comment:

Instrument:

Report

Operator: flindema
ASiQ_2022_01_11_run_01.qps

Date: 2023/11/02

Autosorb iQ Station 1

Analysis gas: Argon87
Analysis Time: 0:41 hr:min
Analysis Mode: Standard
VoidVol. Mode: He Measure

Non-ideality: 3.94e-05 1/Torr

Bath temp.: 87.3 K

Cold Zone V: 2.71203 cc

CellType: 9mm

VoidVol Remeasure: off

Warm Zone V: 14.543 cc

Multi-Point BET

Data Reduction Parameters Data

Adsorbate model	Thermal Transpiration: on	Eff. mol. diameter (D): 3.54 Å	Eff. cell stem diam. (d): 4.0000 mm
	Argon87	Temperature 87.300 K	
	Molec. Wt.: 39.948	Cross Section: 14.200 Å ²	Liquid Density: 1.400 g/ cc

Multi-Point BET Data

Relative Pressure [P/Po]	Volume @ STP [cc/g]	1 / [W((Po/P) - 1)] [1/g]	Relative Pressure [P/Po]	Volume @ STP [cc/g]	1 / [W((Po/P) - 1)] [1/g]
5.03227e-02	6.3734	4.6648e+00	1.99949e-01	8.4112	1.6671e+01
1.00652e-01	7.0988	8.8457e+00	2.51050e-01	9.1893	2.0467e+01
1.50484e-01	7.7432	1.2836e+01	3.00841e-01	9.9966	2.4151e+01

BET summary

Slope = 77.640 1/g
 Intercept = 9.760e-01 1/g
 Correlation coefficient, r = 0.999728
 C constant = 80.546
 Surface Area = 27.229 m²/g